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Determinants of Voluntary Medical Male Circumcision Uptake among Men in Turkana County, Kenya

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Abstract

Introduction: In Kenya, Voluntary Medical Male Circumcision (VMMC) has been identified as a critical intervention to reduce the risk of HIV transmission and improve general male health. Research has shown that circumcised men have a lower likelihood of contracting HIV, particularly in high-prevalence regions of sub-Saharan Africa. This study aimed to assess the determinants of voluntary medical male circumcision in Turkana County, Kenya.

Methods: The study used an analytical cross-sectional design with multi-stage sampling. STATA version 15 was employed for quantitative data analysis, while Slovin's formula determined the sample size, yielding 370 respondents. Both crude and adjusted odds ratios measured associations between variables. Thematic analysis was applied to the quantitative data.

Results: This study revealed a VMMC uptake rate of 64.9%. Multivariate analysis revealed a statistically significant association between VMMC uptake and three key factors: distance to the health facilities (aOR) = 4.7 (p-value < 0.001), education level (aOR = 8.6 (p-value < 0.001), and importance of VMMC aOR = 8.32 (p-value = 0.01).

Conclusions: This study highlights the importance of accessibility, proximity, and educational awareness in the uptake of Voluntary Medical Male Circumcision (VMMC). These findings suggest that to increase VMMC uptake, targeted strategies that address these factors are essential for increasing VMMC uptake.

Keywords: Accessibility to health services; Education level; HIV prevention; Kenya; Voluntary Medical Male Circumcision

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INTRODUCTION

Male circumcision, also known as voluntary medical male circumcision (VMMC), is a scientific method that has been proven to decrease HIV transmission [1]. Circumcision involves removing the protective covering from the top of the penis [2]. This practice has been in existence for centuries, dating back to the ancient times mentioned in religious texts [2]. Voluntary Medical Male Circumcision (VMMC) has emerged as a method to control the rapid global spread of HIV and AIDS, and has become a pandemic affecting numerous countries [3]. Male circumcision is one of the oldest and most widespread medical practices globally and is performed for religious, sociological, scientific, and cultural reasons. Voluntary male circumcision, performed for medical purposes such as hygiene and HIV prevention, involves the surgical removal of the foreskin by qualified medical professionals with the consent of the individual [4]. It has been found to reduce HIV transmission from women to men by 60% [4].

Global surveys indicate that increasing medical male circumcision coverage to 80% in affected countries by 2025 could prevent approximately 22% of HIV infections, resulting in significant cost savings [5]. Circumcision rates vary globally, ranging from less than 5% to over 80% in the United States, with an estimated 30% to 40% of adult males circumcised worldwide by the end of 2015 [4]. The average circumcision rate in sub-Saharan Africa is 62% [6], although there is significant variation among tribes that practice circumcision and those that do not. Circumcisions in this region usually occur later in life. For instance, Swaziland has an 8% circumcision rate, Zimbabwe 10%, Botswana 11%, Malawi 12%, Zambia 13%, Uganda 14%, Namibia 21%, South Africa 25%, Tanzania 70%, Ghana 85%, Nigeria 90%, Angola 90%, Democratic Republic of the Congo 90%, and Ethiopia have 92% [2].

In Kenya, the percentage of men who reported being circumcised increased significantly from 85.0% in 2007 to 91.2% in 2012 [3]. Circumcision charges increased across all areas, with maximum increases of 18.1% and 9.0% in the VMMC priority areas of Nyanza and Nairobi VMMC priority areas, respectively [7]. Among HIV-uninfected and uncircumcised men, approximately half (52.5%) had never been married and 84.6% had discontinued condom use with their regular sexual partners [8].

Male circumcision is not seriously regarded in Turkana County according to the evaluated research literature [9]. As a result, the prevalence of STIs, notably HIV, among non-circumcised men is increasing, resulting in societal stigma, high clinical charges, and discrimination [10]. Currently, the VMMC coverage in Turkana County according to Kenya Health Information Systems (KHIS) data is 12.7% compared to the national level of 84% [11]. Low VMMC uptake is an enabler of continuous HIV transmission. The HIV rate in Turkana County based on the Kenya Population-based HIV Impact Assessment (KENPHIA) 2018 survey is 6.8%. Although other factors have contributed to HIV incidence, apathy for VMMC services plays an impetus role in HIV transmission, consequently putting the community at risk of exponential new cases [12]. Therefore, this study aimed to assess the determinants of voluntary medical male circumcision uptake in Turkana County, Kenya.

METHODS

Study design

An analytical cross-sectional design was used in this study. The design unraveled the determinants of VMMC uptake in Turkana County.

Study area

The study areas were Turkana County, Turkana Central, Turkana North, and Turkana South. 45,368 people live in Lodwar, of an estimated 800,000 people. Approximately 95% of citizens are poor [5], attendance in primary school is low, and dropout rates among women are the highest in Kenya, with only 7% literacy projected among women in the county [13]. Turkana County has 13 hospitals, 19 health centers, and 177 dispensaries, and the average distance to a facility is 35 km [14].

Study population

The study's target population was youthful men, aged 20-49 years in Turkana County. According to the 2019 census, the male population in Turkana County constituted approximately 51.6%. Thus, 51.6% of the population aged 20-49 years of 204, 357 in Turkana County is 105, 449 [14].

Sample size determination

In this study, Slovin's formula was used for sample size calculation, and 370 study respondents were recruited for this study.

Sampling technique

This study used multi-stage sampling. Purposive sampling was used to select three sub-counties, Turkana Central, Turkana North, and Turkana South, with 5776, 2177, and 3277 households, respectively. Systematic sampling was used to obtain a representative sample of households. The K^{th} factor was taken to be 3, meaning that every third household from the previous one was sampled. Simple random sampling was used to select one participant from a household with more than one man aged 20-49 years. To provide more information on the utilization of VMMC from each sub-county, one health officer was selected as the key informant through a purposive sampling technique. Health officers were selected to participate in the study because they were directly involved in the implementation of VMMC programs.

Data collection tools and procedures

The investigator secured authorization from the National Commission for Science, Technology and Innovation and trained a research assistant to support data collection. Questionnaires were administered jointly by the researcher and assistant, yielding quantitative data through a semi-structured format that captured socio-demographic details, uptake levels, awareness dimensions, and accessibility influences related to VMMCS. Qualitative insights were gathered using key informant guides.

Statistical analysis

STATA version 15 was used to analyze the quantitative data. Various statistical techniques have been applied, such as descriptive statistics (frequency and percentage) and inferential statistics (regression analysis). The crude odds ratio (OR) was used to measure the association between independent and dependent variables. All determinants associated with VMMC uptake with a p-value of less than 0.05 under bivariate analysis were subjected to stepwise backward logistic regression to create a model of variables that were subjected to multivariate analysis to identify determinants independently associated with VMMC uptake. The quantitative data were analyzed using thematic analysis.

Ethical aspects

Ethical approval was obtained from the Mount Kenya University Ethics and Research Committee (reference number: MKU/ISERC/3164). Approval was also obtained from the National Commission for Science, Technology, and Innovation (NACOSTI) (reference number 295643). Permission was sought from relevant authorities in Turkana County, including the national and county levels, and the county health department's training committee. The study

respondents were guaranteed confidentiality throughout the study and afterward. Informed consent was obtained from all research participants.

RESULTS

Uptake Of Voluntary Medical Male Circumcision Services

As indicated in Figure 1, 64.9% of the study participants reported having ever received VMMC services, indicating a considerable level of engagement with this healthcare intervention, while 35.1% of the study respondents reported having never received VMMC services.

Figure 1. Uptake Of Voluntary Medical Male Circumcision Services.

Social demographic characteristics of the study respondents

As shown in Table 1, the majority of respondents were from Turkana Central (45.95%) and predominantly aged between 20 and 29 years (63.24%). Notably, a significant portion identified as Christians (81.08%) were married (46.49%), 63.24% had diverse educational backgrounds, and 36.76% had no formal education. Temporary housing emerged as the most prevalent type (49.73%), and a substantial proportion adhered to the Turkana cultural rite (Asapan) (76.22%). Additionally, 61.89% of participants lived within a 5-kilometer radius of a Voluntary Medical Male Circumcision (VMMC) center.

Table 1. Social demographic characteristics of the study respondents.

Variables	Categories	N	%
Age	20-29	233	63.2
	30-39	77	20.5
	40-49	36	9.7
	Above 50	24	6.6
Religion	Christians	300	81.1
	Africa Tradition	49	13.2

	Muslim	15	4.1
	Others	6	1.6
Education level	No Formal Education	136	36.8
	Primary	52	14.1
	Secondary	121	32.7
	Tertiary	61	16.5
Sub-county	Turkana North	63	17
	Turkana Central	170	46
	Turkana South	137	37
Type of house	Temporary	184	49.7
	Semi-Permanent	136	36.8
	Permanent	50	13.5
Marital status	Single	146	39.5
	Divorced	35	9.5
	Widowed	17	4.6
	Married	172	46.4
Distance to VMMC center	Within 5 Km	229	61.9
	More Than 5 Km	141	38.1

Socio-demographic factors associated with uptake of VMMC among men in Turkana County

As shown in Table 2, Individuals aged 30-39 were 4.37 more likely to be circumcised than those aged 50 years and above (cOR=4.37,95% CI= 1.66-11.48, P.value=0.003**). Christians were approximately 2.89 times more likely to take up VMMC services than individuals of other religions(cOR=2.89,95% CI: 1.70-4.92, P.value=< 0.001). The calculated cOR for VMMC uptake in the Turkana South compared to the Turkana Central is remarkably high at 20.89, with a 95% CI of 9.22-47.34. Study respondents with a secondary level of education were 39.2 times more likely to have VMMC uptake than those with no formal education (cOR=39.2,95% CI: 18.3-84.16, P.value= < 0.001). Study participants living in permanent houses were 9.8 more likely to undergo circumcision than those living in temporary houses (cOR=9.8,95% CI: 5.82-16.66, P.value= < 0.001). The crude odds ratio (OR) for VMMC uptake among those living within 5 kilometers was 9.31 (95% CI: 5.06-17.13), indicating a substantially higher likelihood of uptake compared to those living farther away.

These findings agreed with the qualitative data, which one of the key informants narrated: “*When the clinic is just down the road, young men are less likely to delay or avoid the procedure. It’s convenient, and they feel reassured that help is nearby if there are any issues after the procedure...*”(KII 3, 2024).

Table 2. Socio-demographic factors associated with uptake of VMMC.

Variables	VMMC Uptake		COR	95% CI	P Value
	Yes	No			
<i>Age</i>					
20-29	158 (67.52%)	76 (32.48%)	3.47	1.45-8.27	0.005**
30-39	55 (72.37%)	21 (27.63%)	4.37	1.66-11.48	0.003**
40-49	18 (50.00%)	18 (50.00%)	1.67	0.58-4.78	0.342
Above 50	9 (37.50%)	15 (62.50%)		<i>Ref</i>	
<i>Religion</i>					
Christian	209 (69.67%)	91 (30.33%)	2.89	1.70-4.92	0.000**
Others	31 (44.39%)	39 (55.71%)		<i>Ref</i>	
<i>Marital status</i>					
Married	116 (67.44%)	56 (32.56%)	1.24	(0.804-1.9)	0.333
Single	124 (62.63%)	74 (37.37%)		<i>Ref</i>	
<i>Education level</i>					
Primary	44 (84.62%)	8 (15.38%)	19.4	(8.26-45.7)	0.000**
Secondary	111 (91.74%)	10 (8.26%)	39.2	(18.3-84.16)	0.000**
Tertiary	55 (90.16%)	6 (9.84%)	32.4	(12.7-82.5)	0.000*
No formal Education	30 (22.06%)	106 (77.94%)		<i>Ref</i>	
<i>Type of house</i>					
Permanent	163 (87.63%)	23 (12.37%)	9.8	(5.82-16.66)	0.000**
Temporary	77 (41.85%)	107 (58.15%)		<i>Ref</i>	
<i>Distance to Nearest VMMC Centre</i>					
Within 5 km	113 (49.34%)	116 (50.66%)	9.31	(5.06-17.13)	0.000**
More than 5 kms	127 (90.07%)	14 (35.14%)		<i>Ref</i>	
<i>Sub county</i>					
Turkana North	30 (47.62%)	33 (52.38%)	1.02	(0.57-1.82)	0.939
Turkana South	130 (94.89%)	7 (5.11%)	20.89	(9.22-47.34)	0.000**
Turkana Central	80 (47.06%)	90 (52.94%)		<i>Ref</i>	

Influence of Social-Cultural Factors on VMMC Uptake in Turkana County

As shown in Table 3, men who embraced circumcision as a cultural rite were over 4.6 times more likely to have received VMMC services (cOR=4.6,95% CI: 2.37-8.76, P.value= < 0.001). Men who perceived VMMC as holding religious importance were over ten times more likely to undergo circumcision than those who did not (cOR=10.6,95% CI: 2.5-44.7, P.value= < 0.001). However, community perception of circumcised individuals(cOR=1.38,95% CI: 0.9-2.12, P.value= < 0.14),discrimination (cOR=1.52,95% CI: 0.97-2.34, P.value= 0.07), and cultural acceptance of VMMC uptake(cOR=1.48,95% CI: 0.96-2.28, P.value= 0.08) were not statistically associated with the uptake of VMMC.

Table 3. Influence of Social-Cultural Factors on VMMC Uptake in Turkana County.

Variables	VMMC Uptake	COR	95% CI	P Value
Cultural Acceptance				
Yes	103 (70.55%)	1.52	(0.97-2.34)	0.065*
No	137 (61.16%)		<i>Ref</i>	
Community Perception				
Accepted	141 (68.12%)	1.38	(0.9-2.12)	0.140*
Discouraged	99 (60.74%)		<i>Ref</i>	
Most Accepted Cultural Rite				
Circumcision	76 (86.36%)	4.56	(2.37-8.76)	0.000**
Turkana Cultural practice (Asapan)	164 (58.16%)		<i>Ref</i>	
Discrimination				
Yes	103 (70.55%)	1.52	(0.97-2.34)	0.065*
No	137 (61.16%)		<i>Ref</i>	
Importance of VMMC				
Yes	34 (94.44%)	10.56	(2.5-44.7)	0.001**
No	206 (61.68%)		<i>Ref</i>	-

DISCUSSION

The results of the study revealed a VMMC uptake rate of 64.9% among men aged 20-49 in Turkana County, which falls short of the WHO recommended coverage of at least 90%. Another study conducted in Kenya reported a high prevalence of VMMC(79.9%) [7]. Study respondents with a secondary level of education were 39.2 times for likely to have VMMC uptake than those with no formal education. These findings are consistent with those of a study conducted in Tanzania [15]. A higher education level is associated with awareness of VMMC benefits of VMMC.

Christians were approximately 2.89 times more likely to take up VMMC services than individuals of other religions; this finding was concurrent with that of a study carried out in Zimbabwe [16]. Individuals aged 30-39 were 4.37 more likely to be circumcised than those aged 50 years; these findings agreed with those of a study in Zimbabwe [16]. In communities where circumcision is common, young men may feel social pressure to conform to avoid being seen as different or facing potential stigma. This can be especially influential during adolescence, when peer acceptance is often highly valued.

The odds of circumcision increased among study respondents living near a health facility, suggesting that proximity to VMMC facilities plays a crucial role in the decision-making process regarding circumcision uptake. Men living within a closer radius of VMMC centers may find it more convenient and accessible to access these services, leading to a higher uptake rate. Conversely, individuals residing farther away may face logistical challenges or barriers in accessing VMMC centers, resulting in a lower uptake rate. The findings of this study align with those of a study conducted in the Nyanza region of Kenya [17].

The results suggest that participants were at least twice as likely to opt for VMMC compared to (or with) other cultural rites. The findings align with a qualitative study conducted in Kenya [18]. Moreover, the study results suggested

that men in Turkana County were four times more inclined to undergo circumcision compared to those engaging in Turkana cultural practice (Asapan). A possible explanation may be rapid urbanization, which resonates with a study conducted in Turkana that showed stigma against uncircumcised men acting as a catalyst in the uptake of VMMC in urban areas [7]. The study findings showed that despite discrimination, men in Turkana County were at least twice as likely to undergo VMMC. Moreover, the findings also indicated that almost 30 percent of the participants were discouraged by women to undergo VMMC in Turkana County and that VMMC led to a reduction in the height of the manhood and weakness in sexual performance. These findings resonate with a study conducted in Zimbabwe that found that partner refusal, especially for older and married men, was a barrier to VMMC uptake [16].

CONCLUSIONS

The results of the study revealed a VMMC uptake rate of 64.9% among men aged 20-49 in Turkana County, which falls short of the WHO recommended coverage of at least 90%. Multivariate analysis revealed a statistically significant association between VMMC uptake and three key factors: availability of services in health facilities, distance to the nearest health facility, study respondents' education level, and importance of VMMC uptake. This analysis highlights the importance of accessibility, proximity, and educational awareness in the uptake of Voluntary Medical Male Circumcision (VMMC). The availability of VMMC services in health facilities and proximity to these facilities both emerged as significant factors encouraging higher uptake, suggesting that logistical barriers may limit access to VMMC. Additionally, the education level of respondents was positively correlated with VMMC uptake, highlighting the role of awareness in driving acceptance and utilization of the service. These findings suggest that to increase VMMC uptake, targeted strategies that address these factors are essential for increasing VMMC uptake for men's health [18-22].

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Informed Consent Statement: Informed consent was obtained from all subjects involved in the study

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